

HIGH ACCURACY CURE PROCESS SIMULATION OF COMPOSITES BASED ON INTERNAL STRAIN MEASUREMENT

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ABSTRACT

Residual stress causes unexpected shape distortion in composites, leading to premature failure and high manufacturing cost. Cure process optimization is an effective way to reduce residual stress. However, a cure process is currently determined based on trial-and-error, which is high cost especially in manufacturing large-scale composite structures. Therefore, high accuracy process simulation is required. Cure chemical shrinkage is a key element for such highly accurate simulation. Resin cure reaction, however, is complicated to analyze because the resin property continuously changes during contraction. Although previous works implemented resin cure phenomenon into finite element analysis (FEA), they used several cure kinetics models based on indirect measurement (e.g., thermal analysis) in which the effect of pressure and part scale is neglected. Furthermore, these analyses were validated by only shape of cured composite parts and the internal state was not taken into account. Hence, this study aims to develop an advanced cure simulation method based on in-situ measurement and to validate the method using internal strain monitoring. First, we embedded two fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors into a UD CFRP laminate to estimate cure shrinkage and material properties. One of the sensors had long tail (50 mm) from sensing point and the other had short tail (2 mm). The sensor responses differed due to “shear-lag” effect which depends on the stiffness of CFRP. Thus, cure strain and material properties were determined based on the different responses. Next, cure process simulation was carried out for a cross-ply laminate using the material properties determined and the extended path dependent constitutive (EPDC) model proposed in this research. We also fabricated a cross-ply specimen and measured the internal strain using FBG sensors. The experiment results agreed well with the simulation, confirming the validity of the proposed approach from the viewpoint of internal state.

1 INTRODUCTION

Residual stress after cure processes causes unexpected shape distortion of composites, leading to premature failure and low productivity. Cure process optimization is an effective way to reduce residual stress. However, internal stress and strain of composites during cure are difficult to estimate accurately and a cure process is determined based on a lot of trial manufacture, which is high-cost and time-consuming especially for large-scale composite structures (Fig.1) [1]. Therefore, highly accurate cure process simulation is required to set appropriate cure processes in a reasonable manner.

Chemical cure shrinkage and thermal shrinkage cause residual stress after the cure process and thus both of them should be taken into account. Thermal shrinkage of composites in the cooling process is easy to analyze because the resin properties are almost constant, whereas chemical cure reaction is complicated to analyze because the resin properties continuously change during contraction. Although previous works implemented resin cure phenomenon into finite element analysis (FEA), they used several cure kinetics models based on indirect measurement (e.g., thermal analysis) in which the effect of pressure and part scale is neglected. Furthermore, these analyses were validated by only the shape of cured composites parts, and the internal state was not taken into account. Hence, this study aims to

develop an advanced cure simulation method based on in-situ measurement and to validate the method using internal strain monitoring.

Figure 1: Relation between manufacturing risk and scale [1].

2 OUTLINE OF THIS STUDY

Cure process analysis needs a material model, chemical cure shrinkage strain and elastic modulus during cure. Furthermore, the validating method of the analysis is also very important. Features of previous work and our approach are compared in Fig.2, which are described in more detail in the following sections.

	Previous works	This study
Material model	ILE model(Time-consuming) PDC model(Low accuracy)	Extended PDC model (Well-balanced)
Property determining method	Strain Degree of cure: α (Measured by DSC) Long tail FBG sensor	
	Elastic modulus Measured by DMA Short tail FBG sensor Determining by Shear-lag	
	Out of curing conditions	Under curing conditions
Validating method	Internal strain(Exact)	

Figure 2: Features of previous works and this study.

2.1 Material model

In previous work, the Incrementally Linear Elastic (ILE) model [2, 3] and the Path Dependent Constitutive (PDC) model [4] were representatively adopted for a material model. In the ILE model, stress is given by the summation of the incremental elastic solutions from all previous steps. In each step, stress is calculated from multiplication of the elastic modulus and strain change, which are the functions of time or degree of cure. The ILE model is time-consuming, unsuited for calculation of large and complicated FEA. In the PDC model resin state is classified into rubbery state and glassy state, and both of them has a constant value as elastic modulus respectively. The PDC model is simple and practical, although low accurate. Hence the Extended Path Dependent Constitutive (EPDC) model, which is an extension of the PDC model, is proposed in this study. The EPDC model assumes that the material property in a time section as a constant value. The EPDC model is more precise than the PDC

model and quite less time-consuming than viscoelastic models and the ILE model. Stress-strain diagram of a CFRP laminate, which is cured under geometrical constraint and then demolded, is shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3: Schematic of EPDC model and PDC model.

2.2 Cure shrinkage strain

Previous work assumed that volumetric cure shrinkage of the resin bears proportional relationship to the degree of cure. Thus the chemical cure shrinkage strain of the composite was modeled as a linear function of degree of cure [2, 3]. The degree of cure was determined by Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). However, cure pressure, specimen size and effect of reinforcing fibers were not taken into account. In our previous work [5], a direct measurement method was established using embedded Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors. In this study, chemical cure shrinkage strain in a unidirectional CFRP laminate is measured in the same conditions as the practical cure process.

2.3 Elastic modulus during cure

In previous work, Elastic modulus during cure was determined by Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) [6, 7] or modeled as a simple function of degree of cure determined by DSC [2, 3]. However, these are not based on in-situ measurement, and elastic modulus is not obtained on the same conditions as the practical cure process.

In this study, a new method of determining elastic modulus by using a shear-lag effect between the host material and an FBG sensor is proposed (Fig.4). The smaller elastic modulus of the host material, the lower the strain at the edge of the optical fiber is (i.e., amount of shear lag is larger) (Fig.5). Hence, we can determine elastic modulus of the host material by measuring the amount of shear lag. We used two FBG sensors cut at 2mm (i.e., short-tailed FBG sensor) and 50mm (long-tailed FBG sensor) from the measuring points, and evaluated the strain difference between these two sensors due to the shear lag effect. The distance from the edge to the measuring point of the FBG sensor is hereinafter referred to as “tail length”.

Figure 4: Schematic of shear-lag effect.

Fig.5 Shear-lag depending on elastic modulus of matrix resin.

2.4 Validation method

Analyses of previous work were validated by only the shape of cured composite parts, which was measured by a displacement gauge, and the internal state was not taken into account [2-4, 6, 7]. In this study, the analysis is exactly validated based on internal strain measurement of a unidirectional laminate and a cross-ply laminate by FBG sensors.

3 EXPERIMENT FOR DETERMINATING MATERIAL PROPERTIES

FBG sensors (Fujikura Ltd., cladding diameter 125mm, polyimide-casting diameter 150 mm, grating length 1mm) with different tail length of 2 and 50mm were embedded at the through-thickness center of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate (T700S/2592, Toray Industries, Inc., $[0_{50}]$, 100mm×100mm, thickness 7.5mm) (Fig.6). Vacuum bagging films covered both sides of the specimen surface to minimize constraint on the specimen (Fig.7) [5]. Hence, the composite specimen could freely deform in the through-thickness and in-plane transverse directions. The heating rate was set to 2°C/min and the cure temperature was 90°C with 5.0h holding. After cure, the specimen was naturally cooled down.

The result is shown in Fig.6. Strain in 140-320min section is due to chemical cure shrinkage. The strain of the short-tailed FBG sensor is smaller than that of the long-tailed FBG sensor in this section due to the shear-lag effect between the host material and the FBG sensor. The difference of these two FBG sensors in strain increment is large in the early period of cure due to the large shear-lag effect, and the difference decreases as the cure proceeds. This is because Young's modulus of the resin (E_m) increases by the cure and thus the shear-lag effect decreases.

The material properties were determined using this result. First, the cure section was divided into 10 sections. Second, ratio of the strain increment in the short-tailed FBG sensor to that of the long-tailed FBG sensor was evaluated in each section. Finally, using FEA the pair of E_m and in-plane transverse strain (i.e., cure shrinkage) of the composite was determined to reproduce the ratio obtained. E_m and transverse strain of composite in each section are shown in Fig.8. E_m gradually increases as the cure reaction proceeds, and jumps in the final part of the cure. Furthermore, for the comparison, a unidirectional specimen ($[0_{10}]$, thickness 3.0mm) that was cooled down during the cure was tested in DMA to measure the transverse elastic modulus. The measuring mode was the dual cantilever mode with three types of frequency (e.g., 1Hz, 0.1Hz and 0.01Hz). The test temperature was 90°C, which was the same temperature as the cure. Young's modulus of the resin was obtained from the results of DMA measurement by using the Self-Consistent Field model [8] (Fig.8). As the result, E_m depends on the frequency of DMA measurement especially in the early period of the cure. It was found difficult to determine elastic properties of composites during the cure by DMA.

Figure 6: Schematic of the laminate (left) and the result of the experiment for determining material properties (right).

Figure 7: Photograph and schematic of specimen without a tool.

Figure 8: Development of Young's modulus of resin E_m and transverse incremental strain of composites during cure.

4 RESULTS OF ANALYSES AND VALIDATING EXPERIMENT

We used properties of the composite determined in Section 3 to simulate in-plane transverse strain of a unidirectional laminate ($[0_{50}]$) and through-thickness strain of a cross-ply laminate ($[90_8/0_{34}/90_8]$). In the experiment, we embedded FBG sensors in the in-plane transverse direction at the thickness center of the unidirectional laminate and in the through-thickness direction at the in-plane center of the cross-ply laminate, and thus measured internal strain during the cure. Finally, we compared the

experiment results with the simulation to confirm the validity of the proposed approach.

4.1 Validation of in-plane transverse strain of unidirectional laminate

We embedded the FBG sensor with 10mm tail length (middle-tailed FBG sensor) in the in-plane transverse direction at the thickness center of the unidirectional laminate ($[0_{50}]$), and measured in the same conditions as Section 3. In the cure simulation, we used the material property (Fig.8) to calculate the strain of the sensor with EPDC model and PDC model by FEA.

The result is presented in Fig.9. The simulations agree well with the experiment. Especially the EPDC model perfectly reproduced the strain change during the cure process. The result of PDC model is shown as a point because the gradual change in the elastic properties during the cure process was approximated by a single change [4]. Therefore, these results suggested that in-plane stress and strain during cure is accurately analyzed by the proposed approach.

Figure 9: Schematic of the laminate and the result of the experiment that confirms the validity of the in-plane analysis.

4.2 Validation of through-thickness strain of cross-ply laminate

The lower 8 plies were normally laminated, and the others were laminated while inserting a needle to make a small through thickness hole. Then, we inserted a short-tailed FBG sensor into the hole to monitor the through-thickness strain during the cure [5]. Moreover, we used the material properties (Fig.8) to simulate the strain of the short tailed FBG sensor and the in-plane residual stress in the 90 degree layer with EPDC model and PDC model.

The experiment result and the stress and strain simulation result of the EPDC and the PDC are shown in Fig.10. The EPDC model agrees with the PDC model in the strain simulation, whereas not in the stress simulation. This is because material properties of rubbery state are assumed constant in the PDC model. This result suggests that the EPDC model and the material properties determined based on internal strain monitoring are required for accurate cure process analyses.

Figure 10: Schematic of the laminate and the result of the experiment that confirms the validity of the through-thickness analysis.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We developed an advanced cure process simulation method based on strain monitoring by FBG sensors. The present study demonstrated that stress and strain in the both in-plane and through-thickness direction are accurately evaluated by the proposed method. This technique would contribute to weight-saving and cost reduction of various products, such as airplanes. On a final note, further research is necessary on the following subjects in order to confirm the versatility of the proposed method.

- (1) Confirming the validity of the proposed method using other materials than T700S/2592.
- (2) Confirming the validity of the proposed method for complicated parts, such as L-shaped parts or pipes.

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